

Foodborne illnesses caused by bacterial pathogens remain a critical public health challenge worldwide. *Salmonella spp.*, *Shigella spp.*, and pathogenic strains of *Escherichia coli* are among the most common causative agents, leading to diverse disease manifestations that range from mild gastrointestinal symptoms to severe systemic infections. Understanding the pathogenicity, resistance mechanisms, and transmission dynamics of these bacteria is crucial for developing effective control strategies and reducing the burden of foodborne diseases.

Food poisoning outbreaks among humans caused by *Salmonella* spp are very common which happens due to *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Salmonella choleraesuis*, *Salmonella enteritidis* and many other similar species. *Salmonella* resistant to antibiotics including vancomycin, erythromycin, ampicillin and penicillin commonly, multidrug resistance phenotype of *Salmonella* is reported to confer resistance to ampicillin and streptomycin. Food poisonings due to *Salmonella spp* are usually sporadic and, in many cases, there is no identifiable link to other cases as the mode of transmission is evident in majority cases. After incubation period which is 6to 48 hours *Salmonella* releases its causative agents by which *Salmonella* species can cause disease. During infection, it must overcome various host defenses and stomach conditions before reaching the intestinal. At first it can adhere to the lining of the intestines and invade intestinal epithelial cells and after multiplying and cause inflammation. Then, it produces toxins, such as enterotoxins and cytotoxins, which disrupt normal cellular functions, damaging the intestinal lining and impairing fluid absorption. Moreover, its presence triggers an immune response, leading to inflammation which contributes to symptoms like fever, nausea, and abdominal pain. The bacteria can disrupt the normal balance of gut flora, leading to an imbalance that worsens gastrointestinal symptoms such as vomiting and diarrhea. Moreover, *Salmonella* can cause systemic disease, typically not associated with food poisoning, or localized infections leading to enteritis. *Salmonella* adapts using a wide range of virulence genes, including specific virulence genes, housekeeping genes, and regulatory genes.

*Shigella* is the leading cause of diarrheal disease globally and poses a significant public health threat due to its drug resistance, especially in children under five. Shiga toxin is a potent toxin produced primarily by *Shigella dysenteriae* which disrupts protein synthesis

in host cells by inhibiting the function of ribosomes, which can lead to cell death. Because of that it causes severe symptoms in infections, including bloody diarrhea, abdominal pain, and potentially life-threatening conditions like hemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS), which can cause kidney failure. Research shows that out of 474 *Shigella* strains, only two (0.5%) were sensitive to all 21 antimicrobial agents tested and fourteen strains (3.0%) showed co-resistance to third-generation cephalosporins and fluoroquinolones. Investigating its genetic diversity is crucial as 70 *Shigella* strains from children under five, comprising 40 *Shigella dysenteriae* and 30 *Shigella boydii* and among those serotypes 7 (30%), 2 (28%), and 3 (23%) were most common in *S. dysenteriae*, while serotype 2 accounted for 50% of the *S. boydii* isolates.

The bacteria constituting the species *Escherichia coli* are commonly found in the intestinal flora of man and animals. Though most strains are non pathogenic, certain strains might induce disease, because of that *E. coli* should therefore be regarded as a potential pathogenic organism. Pathogenic strains can lead to various disease syndromes, such as distinct diarrheal illnesses, wound infections, meningitis, septicemia, atherosclerosis, hemolytic uremic syndrome, and immunological disorders like reactive and rheumatoid arthritis. The enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC) strains produce one or more of toxins from the heat-labile and the heat-stable enterotoxin families as well as possess specific adhesion fimbriae for intestinal attachment and colonization. Some enteropathogenic *E. coli* strains (EPEC) produce one or more of the cytotoxins, not only that it can adhere to intestinal cells interfering with the electrolyte transport. Moreover, the enterohemorrhagic *E. coli* (EHEC) strains had shown to produce one or more of the cytotoxins (vero-cytotoxins, shiga-like toxins). Food originating from warm-blooded animals may be contaminated with *E. coli*, usually strains causing disease in animals do possess other colonization factors than those found on human pathogenic strains. The recipient of the potential pathogenic *E. coli* through food, the humans, are also at different risk of contracting diseases. The factors of most importance seem to be the immunological and nutritional status of the host. Due to the fact that the latter constitute a part of normal intestinal flora, differentiation between pathogenic and non-pathogenic strains becomes very important.

The pathogenicity and multidrug resistance of *Salmonella spp.*, *Shigella spp.*, and certain *E. coli* strains underline the significant public health threats posed by these bacteria. Each pathogen employs specific virulence mechanisms, ranging from toxin production to host immune evasion, that facilitate infection and disease progression. The growing incidence of antibiotic resistance, particularly among *Shigella* and *Salmonella*, further complicates treatment, underscoring the need for vigilant monitoring and robust public health interventions. In the end we can say that the multidrug resistance and virulence of *Salmonella*, *Shigella*, and certain *E. coli* strains highlight an urgent need for better monitoring and control to protect public health.